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Wave Amplification using a Rapidly Installed Breakwater for WEC Enhanced Performance

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Abstract

A physical model study of the Rapidly Inflatable Breakwater/Wave Amplifier (RIB/WA) was conducted at the OH Hinsdale Wave Research Laboratory at Oregon State University, to evaluate the wave amplification characteristics of the RIB/WA and potential for application to increase the sea state of calmer waters. The physical model tests were carried out in the Directional Wave Basin and were supported by the DOE-funded TEAMER Program. A 1:24 scale model of a pair of 107 m (350-ft) long by 6.1m (20-ft) diameter water filled and pressurized elastomer coated fabric bladders, arranged in a 'V' configuration, was tested over a range of regular and random sea-state conditions. The open 'V' of the RIB/WA system faces the direction of the incoming waves thereby enhancing their amplitude within the area bounded by the 'V'. During testing, the basin was fitted with 16 wave gauges and Qualisys Motion Tracking System was used to measure the free surface within the 'V' of the RIB/WA using floating reflective markers, while additional markers were attached to the bladder to measure its three-dimensional deformation under waves. The model ability to amplify the wave field was measured at three depths, of 1.0 m, 0.75 m, and 0.50 m. This represents two regimes of RIB/WA performance as a function of the under-keel clearance, namely Large Gap and Small Gap. At this scale, a large gap occurs at a depth of 1 m while a small gap occurs at depths of both 0.75 m and 0.50 m. Characteristics affecting RIBWA performance were also measured such as the apex separation of the legs, the internal pressure, wave period, wave height, and wave direction. The ability of the RIB/WA to amplify the wave field was then documented in order to provide feedback on the acceptable and optimal conditions to operate the RIB/WA, as well as to determine areas where more detailed testing would be desired. The results indicate that the RIB/WA at peak can amplify the energy content of the wave field by 1.9 for regular waves and 1.8 for random waves.

Keywords: Wave amplification; Floating Bladders; Wave Energy Converters; Laboratory Experiments; TEAMER

1. Introduction

The 'Rapidly Installed Breakwater/Wave Amplifier' (RIB/WA) is designed to focus ocean waves increasing their amplitude such that they enhance the power generation capabilities of a broad range of wave energy devices in low sea-state conditions offshore. Typically, wave energy devices do not perform efficiently in low wave environments,

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such as prevailing calm weather, or at sheltered areas (bays, estuaries and lakes). The RIB/WA focuses the predominant oncoming waves within the open 'V' formed by the two floating RIB/WA units, thereby enhancing the wave amplitude to excite an individual or an array of wave energy devices installed within the 'V'.

The 'Rapidly Installed Breakwater' (RIB) system as designed, engineered, and tested by the MJPA/QED, Inc. team, is a mature technology that has been evaluated in both wave tank and large-scale field test programs in open sea conditions. The 'Rapidly Installed Breakwater/Wave Amplifier' (RIB/WA) is an adaptation of the RIB system wherein the typical 'V' configuration is oriented with the open legs of the 'V' facing towards the oncoming waves to focus them. This is opposite to the RIB configuration whereby the apex of the 'V' faces towards the oncoming waves to form a calm area afforded by the breakwater legs (see Figure 1 below).

Fig. 1. (a) A prototype scale RIB during a field demonstration of the sheltering effect inside the 'V'; (b) A model scale RIB/WA during testing showing the focusing potential of wave energy.

The Wave Energy industry will benefit from both the wave amplification in calm conditions and the proven ability of the RIB to provide a temporary calm area in waves for the safe emplacement or maintenance of wave energy equipment.

The objective of the tests is to carefully measure the amplitude of waveforms inside the 'V' compared to the external waveforms outside the focused area to determine the overall increase in wave amplification within the 'V'. A range of waveforms were tested with varying directions and sea state conditions. Moreover, different configurations of the RIB/WA were also be tested, including variations in the under-keel clearance, internal pressure and opening angle of the 'V'. Moreover, measurement of the deformation of the RIB/WA will enable the computation of the longitudinal stresses aimed to the selection of the adequate elastomer fabric.

2. Model Layout

2.1. The RIB/WA Technology and basin principles of operation

The RIB/WA consists of a pair of seawater filled watertight bladder tubes pressurized to a desired level of bending stiffness. Each bladder comprises a sealed membrane tube containing the pressurized seawater encased within an exoskeleton structural matrix of webbing that resists the primary tensile loads generated by the seawater pressurized bladders. Typically, the two bladder units (hereinafter called 'legs') are arranged in a 'V' formation. The tubular RIB legs have been designed and fabricated up to 30-ft (~9 m) diameter and several hundred feet long. The choice of full-scale RIB leg diameter and length is based upon both the water depth in the intended area of operation and the specific application of the system. The pressurized RIB/WA resists and focusses the wave forces by stiffening the exoskeleton support structure. Special fittings are provided for attaching the structure to the mooring system at either end. The bladder is provided with valves and fittings for rapidly filling and emptying the system during deployment and recovery. The RIB/WA has built-in closed-cell foam buoyancy which floats it at the nominal water surface. Buoyancy tubes are connected to the top of the RIB/WA to minimize wave over-topping and stabilize roll.

2.2. The RIB/WA Model Test Apparatus - Description

The RIB/WA model comprises two water-inflated and pressurized bladders fabricated from a lightweight, PVC coated nylon fabric that is impermeable to water. The bladders measure 4.57 m (15-feet) long and 0.25 m (10-inches) in diameter when fully inflated (see Figure 2 below). Each bladder tube section is sealed at one end with a PVC coated fabric hemisphere and a flattened 'toothpaste-tube' type design at the other. Mooring attachments are provided at both ends. Strips of lightweight, flexible, closed cell flotation foam are positioned inside each bladder so that, when filled with water, the bladders float at the water surface with approximately 90 to 95% immersion. On the top surface of each bladder a pair of longitudinal, air-filled flexible PVC tubes are attached that serve as wave overtopping devices.

A plenum chamber connected to the bladders can be raised and/or lowered to maintain a controlled water pressure within each RIB/WA tube. The vertical measurement from the top of the water surface in the plenum chamber relative to the top of the mean water surface in the wave basin provides a fixed pressure inside the bladders.

Fig. 2. (a) RIB/WA Model – Longitudinal view of the basin bladder design. (b) RIB/WA Model – Plan view with the closed apex configuration.

2.3. Experimental Facility

The Directional Wave Basin (DWB) at Oregon State University was used to test the RIB/WA model in a variety of wave conditions and model configurations. The DWB is 48.8 m long and 26.5 m wide, with 2.1 m high walls and a maximum still water depth of 1.5 m. The wave maker of the DWB is a 30-channel piston-type belt-driven servomotor system with 29 paddles arranged as a vertically hinged (snake-type) machine, capable of generating regular, irregular, tsunami-type and user-defined multi-directional waves, and is fitted with an active reflected wave cancellation system.

2.4. Instrumentation

Free surface

The free surface was measured with surface-piercing, resistive wave gauges as well as ultrasonic wave gauges. Sixteen probes were placed in the basin, including 10 probes in a double CERC star directional array to assess the incident and reflected directional wave spectrum, as well as wave gauges surrounding the RIB/WA model to identify wave amplification and attenuation, in the form of wave reflection, diffraction and radiation.

Wave gauges deployed within the RIB/WA can be seen in Figure 3.a.

Motion Tracking

Qualisys® Motion Tracking System was used to measure the free surface displacement as well as the deflections of the RIB/WA along its main axis. Motion tracking is technique of recording motions of bodies by detecting relevant points (markers) non-intrusively with cameras sensitive to infrared light emitted by the camera itself. After proper

calibration, the system provides three-dimensional coordinates of the markers and, if necessary, include algorithms to create rigid bodies as a combination of several markers with constant relative distance.

By placing floating markers at the free surface, Qualisys is able to record the water vertical displacement and, hence, wave conditions.

Markers installed along the RIB/WA, enable the measurement of deflections of the floating body, which can be related to wave amplification or longitudinal stresses of the fabric for a given internal pressure of the RIB/WA.

Markers for tracking the free surface and the deflections of the RIB/WA are seen in Figure 3.b.

Fig. 3. (a) Layout of wave gauges within the RIB/WA. (b) Layout of Qualisys markers for motion tracking within the RIB/WA.

3. Test Conditions and Results

Different wave conditions and model configurations were executed in order to quantify the performance of the RIB/WA in terms of wave amplification (or, equivalently, wave energy amplification). For all wave conditions and water depths, undisturbed tests (i.e. in the absence of the RIB/WA model) were executed for direct comparison purposes. Then, different model configurations were explored, including:

- RIB/WA under-keel clearance. Defined as the distance between the sea floor and the lowest point of the bladder cross-section. It is, in fact, the blocking ratio of the RIB/WA preventing wave transmission, and enhancing wave reflection, increasing the constructive interference of the incident and reflected waves, focusing between the bladders of the RIB/WA. It is expected to be the most significant factor impacting the wave energy amplification. For classification purposes, a Large Gap is defined when the RIB/WA diameter covers no more than 50% of the water depth. A Small Gap is defined with the RIB/WA covers more than 50% of the water column.
- Apex opening distance. Defined as the distance between the shoreside ends of the RIB/WA. Expected to decrease the amplification as this distance increases, this configuration is expected to be required to modify the relative angle with the incident waves, reduce mooring loads and overtopping.
- Internal RIB/WA pressure. The internal pressure of the RIB/WA was controlled by the elevation of the plenum chamber. Increase in the internal pressure will increase the bladder stiffness, which is expected to increase wave amplification by reducing the response of the floating structure to relatively short waves. However, higher pressures will require stronger construction materials that may increase production costs.

The role of the incident wave conditions and different water depths were also investigated. Wave conditions were defined by:

- Wave type (regular and irregular waves). Regular waves were tested to investigate the individual response of the RIB/WA to wave frequency and wave height. Then, irregular waves were simulated representing a more realistic case.
- Wave height. It is expected that the response of the RIB/WA as well as the wave energy amplification is non-linear, i.e. changes in the wave height may have different wave amplification factors.

- Wave period. Wave reflection and transmission is, fundamentally, a dispersive process, governed by the wavelength that is, in turn, a function of the water depth and the wave period. This is particularly true for structures partially covering the water column.
- Wave direction. As a floating structure, the RIB/WA performance depends on the mooring system, i.e. how stationary is. Hence, the relative position of the RIB/WA bladders to the incident and reflected wave directions will be fixed for a given incident wave. The optimal orientation of the RIB/WA is parallel to the incident wave direction, and changes in wave directionality will impact the wave energy amplification.
- Water depth. Since the model RIB/WA has a constant diameter, the variation of the water depth predominantly modifies the RIB/WA under-keel clearance, as described above. However, variations in the water depth will also have an impact on the wavelength for equivalent wave periods. This is due to the expected response of the RIB/WA and the wave energy amplification as a function of the ratio between the bladder length and the wavelength.

Each of the RIB/WA configuration, as well as the wave and water level conditions were investigated thoroughly. A smart approach was selected to reduce the number of experiments, since the access to the facility via TEAMER was limited to 19 days. The wave amplification factor was defined as the ratio between the average wave height for a given configuration and sea state, over the average wave height for the undisturbed conditions and the same sea state. Figure 4 shows the wave amplification factor for a selected series of RIB/WA configurations.

Fig. 4. (a) Effect of the wave period on the wave amplification factor for Large Gap (depth of 1 m) and Small Gap (depths of 0.75 m and 0.5 m). $H=5$ cm, Pressure=20.7 kPa and no apex separation. (b) Effect of the internal RIB/WA pressure on the wave energy amplification factor for Large Gap (depth of 1 m) and Small Gap (depths of 0.75 m and 0.5 m). $H=5$ cm, $T=1.2$ s and no apex separation.

4. Conclusions

Test result analysis indicates that the RIB/WA can amplify the amplitude of the wave field on average by 1.4 times for regular waves and 1.2 times for random waves representing an increase in energy content of on average 1.85 and 1.6 times, respectively. This suggests a substantial motion gain for a system of WECs located within the bounds of the 'V' configuration. Characteristics that were found to affect RIB/WA performance, including a discussion of the optimal conditions for the use of the RIB/WA, are presented.

To further the understanding of the RIB/WA system's capabilities, a natural next step would be larger model scale (e.g., 1:12) tests, that would include similarly scaled prototype WECs, located within the 'V' configuration. The optimal location of WECs within the 'V' configuration is of particular interest to obtain maximum efficiency. This next step, in combination with a cost-benefit analysis of a full-scale RIB/WA system, would provide the necessary confidence to develop field-test capable systems for offshore deployment in selected mild sea-state environments.

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